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Relativistic effects on phaseshift in frequencies invalidate time dilation II

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Abstract: Relative time emerges from relative frequencies. It is the phase shift in relative frequencies due to infinitesimal loss in wave energy and corresponding enlargement in the wavelengths of oscillations; which occur in any clock between relative locations due to the relativistic effects or difference in gravitational potential; result error in the reading of clock time; which is wrongly presented as time dilation.

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1. Introduction

The Theory of Relativity adopts Minkowski spacetime that combines three-dimensional Euclidean space and fourth dimensional time into a four-dimensional manifold, wherein time is robbed of its independence, rather considered 'natural'.

The Theory of Relativity also conveys that the proper time is dependent on relativistic effects and expressed as $t < t'$, where t' is time dilation.

The equation of time dilation is $t' = t/\sqrt{(1 - v^2/c^2)}$ where t' is dilated time, t is proper time, v is relative speed, and c is the speed of light in free space.

The points in consideration here are –

- 'Proper time' including 'relative time' is not natural or the event itself but an emerging concept, mathematical in character.
- 'Space' is not natural or eventual itself but a three-dimensional extent as a mathematical concept.
- Whether 'spacetime,' which combines three-dimensional Euclidean space and fourth-dimensional time into a four-dimensional manifold, is not natural, nor eventual itself, nor dependent on relativistic effects but a four-dimensional extent as a mathematical concept.
- Whether time is not distorted due to relativistic effects.

The conjectural equation of time dilation was based on Doppler's formula,

which failed to identify any cause of time distortion. Whereas the wave equation; in the properties of a wave, in combination with the Planck equation has been able to successfully identify the distorted frequencies due to the relativistic effect that has the influence factor. The distorted frequencies in the equation yield a relative value of time for the corresponding wavelength dilation, which is erroneously known as time dilation.

This expression for time in time dilation contradicts the expression $t=t'$ as in classical mechanics, where time is absolute. Stephen Hawking upheld the concept of imaginary time in his book "The Universe in a Nutshell". Time is defined as the indefinite continued progression of events in the past, present and future existences and considered as a whole, succeeding in irreversible and uniformed succession, which is referred to in the fourth dimension above the three spatial dimensions. Therefore, events invoke time but not vice versa. What special relativity represents in time dilation is not time, and time dilation does not have time. It is rather error in the clock oscillation.

Counterexamples such as experiments made on piezoelectric crystal oscillators show that wave distortions correspond to time distortions due to relativistic effects, thus disproving the conjectural equation of time dilation; and invalidates time dilation altogether. The time dilation equation $t' = t/\sqrt{(1 - v^2/c^2)}$ is wrong.

2. A scientific misconception in time dilation

Events invoke time. The defect in the equation $t' = t/\sqrt{(1 - v^2/c^2)}$ is that relativistic effects, such as speed or gravity of the real events, can never interact with the proper time (t) referred to in the fourth dimension. This means, the $\{1/\sqrt{(1 - v^2/c^2)}\}$ part of the equation cannot influence or interact with the proper time (t) to enlarge it and get the time dilation (t') as in the equation. The piezoelectric crystal oscillators show that the error in wave corresponds to time shift due to relativistic effects.

The observations made on the effect of dark energy do not show anti-gravity, caused by dark energy, affects time in any manner, except causing enlargement in the wavelength due to expansion of space. It is naturally unauthorized and disprovable to enlarge the scale of proper time, instead of distortion in the wavelength of clock oscillation.

Even very small changes in the gravitational forces (G-force) cause internal particles of matter to interact with each other, which is known to cause stresses and associated deformations in the internal matter.

Wavelength distortions, due to the phase shift in relative frequencies, correspond exactly to time distortion; through the relationship $\lambda \propto T$, where λ denotes the wavelength and T denotes the period of oscillation of the wave. So that relativistic effects, such as speed or gravitational potential differences, affect the clock mechanism because of phase shifts in the frequencies and corresponding increase in the wavelength of the clock oscillation, resulting errors in reading of the clock time, but incorrectly perceived as time dilation.

Real events in space never reach the fourth direction of time, either through interactions or relativistic effects such as motion or gravity. Events within space will not have a natural reach toward the dimension of proper time, so that eventual effects can never affect proper time beyond its ideal succession, to obtain time dilation. A clock reading should always follow the order of time sequence; otherwise, the external distortion will cause incorrect readings in the clock mechanism. The dimension of time is considered abstract rather, conceptual.

It would be wrong to try to change proper time like in the conjectural equation of time dilation. Relativistic effects cannot interact with proper time to get time dilation. Apart from this, the concept of time dilation defies the conventional scientific definition of time involving existence and events. Proper time should never be stripped of its independence and retained as 'natural' even in the four-dimensional continuum of space-time. There is no time dilation anywhere; instead, the dilation of the wavelength of the clock oscillation causing errors in the clock time. Wavelength distortions mathematically correspond exactly to time distortions; as in $\lambda \propto T$.

3. General Foundations:

- I. Time is called T , the period of oscillation, so that $T = 2\pi/\omega$. The reciprocal of the period, or the frequency f , in oscillations per second, is given by the expression $f = 1/T = \omega/2\pi = E/h = v/\lambda$. Where h is Planck constant, f, v, λ, T and E respectively represent frequency, velocity,

wavelength, time period and Energy of the wave.

- II. Doppler shift is the change in frequency of a wave in relation to an observer who is moving relative to the wave source.
- III. Time distortion always originates from wavelength distortion but the time dilation of special relativity is not understood from wavelength distortion and so it does not follow the general rules.
- IV. Special relativity does not escape the fundamental equivalence between wavelengths and time, which is much more general than special relativity.
- V. Distortions of wavelengths exactly correspond to time distortions $\lambda \propto T$.
- VI. Time is the indefinite continued progress of existence and events in the past, present, and future regarded as a whole, succeeding in irreversible and uniformed succession, referred to in the fourth dimension above three spatial dimensions. Therefore, time is not what special relativity presents as in time dilation and there is no time in time dilation. It is rather error the in wave.
- VII. Time is an imperceptible fourth dimensional concept so protected from relativistic effects like speed or gravity, nor it subject to real interference or influence or interaction with the cosmic events. The events rather invoke time.
- VIII. The term cosmic time signifies a relationship between the time since the Big Bang and the events within the Universe. The distortion in proper time always originates from wavelength

distortion, including in special relativity, and therefore proper time subject to synchronization with ideal time in near approximation, as done with the atomic clocks.

4. Experimental results:

Experiments made in electronic laboratories on piezoelectric crystal oscillators show that the wave corresponds to time shift due to relativistic effects.

We get the wavelength λ of a wave is directly proportional to the time period T of the wave, that is $\lambda \propto T$, derived from the wave equation $f = v/\lambda = 1/T = E/h$, where h is Planck constant and f, v, λ, T and E represent frequency, velocity, wavelength, time period and Energy of the wave respectively.

Whereas the time interval $T(deg)$ for 1° of phase is inversely proportional to the frequency (f). We get a wave corresponding to the time shift.

For example, 1° phase shift on a 5 MHz wave corresponds to a time shift of 555 picoseconds (ps).

We know, 1° phase shift = $T/360$.

As $T = 1/f$,

1° phase shift = $T/360 = (1/f)/360$.

For a wave of frequency $f = 5 \text{ MHz}$, we get the phase shift (in degree $^\circ$)

= $(1/5000000)/360$

= 5.55×10^{-10}

= 555 ps.

Therefore, for 1° phase shift for a wave having a frequency $f = 5 \text{ MHz}$, and so wavelength $\lambda = 59.95 \text{ m}$, the time shift (time delay) $\Delta t = 555 \text{ ps}$ (approx).

Moreover, for 360° phase shift or, 1 complete cycle for a wave having frequency

1Hz (of a 9192631770 Hz wave); the time shift (time delay)

$\Delta t = 0.0000001087827757077666$ ms (approx).

Time shift of the caesium-133 atomic clock in the GPS satellite: The GPS satellites orbit at an altitude of about 20,000 km. with a time delay of about 38 microseconds per day.

For 1455.50003025° phase shift (or, 4.043055639583333 cycles) of a 9192631770 Hz wave; time shifts (time delays)

$\Delta t = 0.0000004398148148148148$ ms

(approx) or, 38 microsecond time is taken per day.

5. Conclusion:

The phase shifts of frequency due to gravitational potential differences or relativistic effects correspond to dilation of wavelengths of the clock oscillation, which show errors in the clock reading and are misrepresented as time dilation. Time dilation is actually wavelength dilation.

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